

SEMIZLIK VA METABOLIK SINDROMDA BIOIMPEDANS ANALIZATORINI O'RGANISH VA NATIJALARNI TAHLIL QILISH

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Tadqiqot maqsadi. Semizlik bilan kasallangan bemorlarning tana vazn indexiga baho berish. Bioimpedans analizatori orqali semiz va metabolik sindromi bor bemorlarni tekshirib, ko'rsatkichlar ustida ishlash va solishtirish. Metabolik sindromning belgilari o'zgarishini tahlil qilish. Semizlikka turmush tarzini qay darajada ahamiyatli ekanini o'rganish. Sog'lom ovqatlanish va faol hayot tarzini shu bemorlarda qo'llab natijalarni solishtirish.

Materiallar va usullar. Toshkent Tibbiyot Akademiyasi 2-klinikasi klinikasida qandli diabet II tip bilan og'riqan 30 ta bemor olindi. Ulardan 18 tasi ayol, 12 tasi erkak bo'lib 22 yoshdan 60 yoshgacha, o'rtacha yoshi $43,2 \pm 0,5$ yosh. Bemorlarda davo choralaridan, sog'lom turmush tarziga o'tib kunida 10000 qadam sistemasida faol hayotga o'tgandan so'ng dinamikada tana vazn indexi (TVI), laborator tekshituvlardan qonda glyukoza, lipid spektri, HOMA-IR, glikirlangan gemoglobin tekshirildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, sog'lom turmush tarziga o'tishidan oldin va sog'lom turmush tarziga o'tgandan keyin bemorlarning hayot sifati sezilarli yaxshilandi. Tana vazn indexi davodan oldin 41 va davodan so'ng 35. Och qoringa glyukoza miqdori operatsiyadan oldin $9,2 \pm 0,2$, operatsiyadan keyin $5,4 \pm 0,3$. Lipid aterogenligi operatsiyadan oldin 3,1, davodan keyin 2,7. Glikirlangan gemoglobin davodan oldin 10,6, davodan keyin 7,1. Davodan oldin 12 ta (60%) bemorda tungi apnoe holati kuzatilgan, davodan keyin 7 ta (35%) bemorda kuzatildi. Sog'lom turmush tarzi va faol hayot tarziga o'tgandan keyin bemorlarda 100% yaxshilanish kuzatildi. Asoratlar yo'q. Natijalar Bioimpedans orqali tekshirilganda teri ostidagi yog', visseral yog' va TVI pasaygan, tanadagi va hujayralararo suv miqdori normaga kelgan, mushak miqdori ko'paygan, moddalar almashinuvidan chiqqan kkal miqdori kamaygan u esa o'z o'rnida bemorning sog'ayishiga va tanada yog' zahirasini kamayishiga olib kelgan.

Xulosa. Kuzatuv va tahlillarga asoslanib turmush tarzini faol hayot bilan almashtirib, to'g'ri ovqatlanish qoidalariga rioya qilgan bemorlarda semizlik darajasi va metabolik sindrom alomatlari kamaydi. Asoratlar va bemorlarning laborator natijalarini solishtirganda davodan keyingi bemorlarning hayot sifati sezilarli darajada yaxshilandi.

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